

GLOBAL FUTURE, SYSTEMIC CHALLENGES Changes in the Profiles of Law?

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Confronting (1) *Challenges in Need of Direct Response*, how to react if, by inventing easy-to-use facilities, personality can be manipulated, programmed, changed all through? if abortion can be achieved through organic regression? if undetectable arms will be developed with long delayed or far reaching effect? if chemical, radioactive or cyber warfare is made available on a mass scale as operated by anyone in isolation with no chance of identification? if life expectations of human groups can be worsened or changed? or, if the reason of copyright regulation is lost, as technological innovation excludes any chance of control? With (2) *New Dimensions of Law*, how law reacts if it will be given multiplied presence, global level of orderliness (arranged “in books”) and globally centralised focus (practiced “in action”), with technics intensifying scope and depth of regulation? Moreover, (3) *Changes in Law* are also to occur as a consequence of basic changes in how humans are organised into society and in the technology by which their conduct are influenced. For instance, information technology will be enabled to process millions of opinions and to call masses for public actions, with civil society superseding politically organised society. As to technics, one may recall how mass media have assisted in implementing social changes and mass manipulation been resorted to recently in both dictatorial and democratic regimes. Lastly, (4) *Change of Paradigms in the Understanding of Social Order* is also a new phenomenon: investigation into individual factors (i.e., causes/energies/effects) in chains of (quasi-)causality gets replaced by a vision built on average of what can be experienced in statistic masses and probabilities. For an autopoietic process, the coordinates (or laws) of ongoing operations are getting defined through (while and for) the operational process itself, individually for each case. Accordingly, the »order out of chaos« idea is becoming an explanatory principle for the legal field as well.

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Law is only distinct in so far as there is an institutional claim that posits distinctiveness a notional *sine qua non*.¹ As an agent in action, however, law is never detached from the human component and the latter’s sociality. At the

¹ By Philip Selznick, ‘The Sociology of Law’ in *Sociology Today Problems and Prospects*, ed. Robert K. Merton, Leonard Broom, Leonard S. Cottrell (New York: Basic Books 1959), pp. 125–127 at p. 124 and ‘Sociology of Law’ *International Encyclopedia of the Social Sciences* 9 (New York: Macmillan 1968), pp. 50–59 at p. 50.

same time, as an aggregate of abstract conceptual categories, the law reflects intersubjective relations as universally typifiable social relations transformed into jural relations, which serves self-justification within its own system of fulfilment as a quasi-logical consequence and its perpetuation/enforcement with questioning excluded. Thereby social order is mediated by legal order as the final and supreme factor of social integration.

What needs (re)olution here, according to whatever general standard, is a conglomerate of human interests, with arising tensions and their opposition. KARL MARX and CARL SCHMITT equally described how human interests, even particular ones, have ever been asserted as universalised ones in history² and how laws, both ancient and more contemporary ones, were got a stamp of legitimisation by referring to their godly roots or natural law foundation or, particularly in present times, being sprung/deduced from human rights. Human manipulation and ideological intervention notwithstanding,³ our intellectual world is ours: we are at home in it and routinised within it.⁴ It gets perceived and cognised via presuppositions mediated by socialisation and education ceaselessly,⁵ the framework of which is pegged out by universalised moral principles lived through as the natural condition of human existence,⁶ and also shaped by human imagination⁷ within the bounds of what is conceived as normality.⁸

² Karl Marx & Friedrich Engels *The German Ideology* [Die deutsche Ideologie] I–II, 3rd revised edition (Moscow: Progress Publishers 1976) or, in original language, <http://www.mlwerke.de/me/me03/me03_009.htm>.

³ FRIEDRICH NIETZSCHE identified *Willen zur Macht* in human conceptuality as well, as part of pressure widely exercised by those stronger, worthy to rule; cf. <http://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wille_zur_Macht>.

⁴ See, e.g., Dirk Baecker *Wozu Kultur?* 2nd enlarged edition (Berlin: Kadmos Kulturverlag 2001) 203 pp.

⁵ This is not a reference to pre-comprehension [*Vorverständnis*] within hermeneutic circle but knowledge backing whatever social consensus, seldom made conscious. Cf. Csaba Varga *The Paradigms of Legal Thinking* [1996/1999] 2nd enlarged edition (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2012) 418 pp. [Philosophiae Iuris] & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14600/14657/>>. It was Chaïm Perelman *Droit, morale et philosophie* (Paris: Librairie Générale de Droit et de Jurisprudence 1968) 149 pp. [Bibliothèque de Philosophie du Droit VIII] to reveal that our opinions are based on series of conventionalisations made by the human kind on the scene of a “universal auditorium” [*auditoire universelle*], justifying only in case of deviation or reformulation, and otherwise preserving the routine by unreflected imitation.

⁶ For natural law based on the anthropological presuppositions of Jewish, Christian, and Islamic theology, the human quality is defined once and for all by the act of creation. This was somewhat mitigated through realising its historically variable contents [*Naturrecht mit wechselndem Inhalt*] by Rudolf Stammeler *Wirtschaft und Recht nach der materialistischen Geschichtsauffassung Eine sozialphilosophische Untersuchung* (Leipzig: Veit 1896) viii + 668 pp. at p. 183. For MARXISM, however, albeit the human species-essence [*Gattungswesen*] — see <http://www.marx-forum.de/marx-lexikon/lexikon_g/gattung.html> — appears as constant, it is, in an analytic-conceptual approach, a historical product, part of the second nature of humans, derivative of underlying conditions. At the same time, MARXISM holds, it is ideologically coloured, in the sense that it results, in any of its given forms, from human reflection.

⁷ As to the law's preassumptions, seldom specified or defined, cf. James Boyd White *The Legal Imagination Studies in the Legal Thought and Expression* (Boston: Little Brown 1973) xxxv + 986 pp.

⁸ Carl Schmitt *Politische Theologie Vier Kapitel zur Lehre von der Souveränität* (Berlin & Leipzig: Duncker & Humblot 1922) 56 pp. <<http://de.scribd.com/doc/81214206/schmitt-politische-theologie>> argues with normality conceived of as the natural presupposition of any conscious regulation, concluding to that responding to exceptional situations needs a *hic et nunc* concrete norm to be found or posteriorly construed.

Globalism is a politically motivated process the new potentialities of which are afforded by the contemporary scientific and technological revolution. Without prophesising on its possible outcomes either in perspectives of a coming world economy or world society, it can be taken for granted that our present-day law's conceptual network, axiomatised by conventionalised principles within an ideally coherent system, will be wholly or partly shaken with consequences unforeseen.

1. Challenges in Need of Direct Response

Technological development ceaselessly raise challenges that are to be responded instantly. Biotechnics, nanotechnics, physical and chemical reconsiderations on both macro and micro level from armament to pharmacology and, last but not least, social explosion that may arise from new achievements of information technology, that is, a series of new actors/factors may become the source of new dangers, crying, as imminent calls, for regulation on a global scale—such as what to do with space or atomic garbage or with technologies that make information multiplication and distribution uncontrollable, for instance.

Accordingly, foundational values and basic principles are eminently targeted, with an urge to reconsider them, their reflective equilibrium,⁹ and the new — still tolerable — balance amongst them, with no hope of much reliable prognostication. Well, how to react if, by inventing easy-to-use facilities, personality can be manipulated, programmed, changed all through? if abortion can be achieved through (as replaced by) organic regression? if undetectable arms will be developed with long delayed or very far reaching effect? if chemical, radioactive or cyber warfare is made available on a mass scale, which is easy to operate by one single person in isolation, under conditions when there will remain no genuine chance to identify the wrongdoer?¹⁰ if life expectations of human groups, either genetically specified or otherwise targeted, can be worsened or changed, almost at please and with no trace posteriorly successfully detectable? or, if there will be no reason any longer for copyright regulation, as technological innovation will by itself exclude any chance of control?

⁹ Cf. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflective_equilibrium>, originating in John Rawls *A Theory of Justice* (Cambridge, Mass.: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press 1971) v + 607 pp.

¹⁰ For the British Special Air Service Gibraltar action practically executing three Irish Republican Army/Active Service Unit agents on March 6, 1988, see <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Operation_Flavius> & <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Death_on_the_Rock>, with complaint dismissed by the European Court of Human Rights, see *McCann and Others v United Kingdom* Series A, No 324, Application No 18984/91(1995) in <<http://www.leeds.ac.uk/law/hamlyn/gibraltar.htm>>. As to practically undetectable wrongdoing, with effect of troubling (to crashing) basic working systems, cf. <<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cyberwarfare>> and Johann-Christoph Woltag *Cyber Warfare Military Cross-border Computer Network Operations under International Law* (Mortsel: Intersentia 2014) xviii + 314 pp. [International Law 14].

As known, technology is used to be seen as merely instrumental and, as such, quite neutral a function. However, lessons that can be drawn from 20th century brutalities show parallelity between the technological achievement of producing big earth moving machines like bulldozers, on the one hand, and genocides perfected on almost an industrial mass scale, on the other, so that the apparently deep human inclination to murder fellow creatures for political reasons could only materialise at a time when bulldozer machines were already invented and thereby it became possible to take over and move any amount of physical weight to another place and to reassemble it at please, involving the burial of human bodies, their concealment deep in the soul or dissipation in water streams.¹¹ Perhaps it is not by chance that visions on the philosophy of history like OSWALD SPENGLER's *The Decline of the West* have for long been associated with the idea of technological self-development with technical processes becoming autotelic as a factor in the death of varying civilisations.¹²

Who will then decide in technologically relevant issues? Following the direction of the development of post *legal positivism* having transformed into *legal socio-positivism* (transubstantiating judicial process into a multi-actor intercultural and multi-criterial discourse),¹³ decision will certainly be done or prepared by experts' panels, presupposing not more demand on behalf of lawyerly assistance than mere channelling, drafting, and internal coherence testing—only provided that it will not be followed by American-type re-juridification again, wedging the lawyers' cast in the process again, in order to regain for the latter the monopoly of control, diverting the whole, socially all-inclusive process into American-type jurisprudence.¹⁴

2. New Dimensions of Law

Due to ongoing technological revolution, the legal phenomenon may gain new dimensions if it is given, among others, multiplied presence, qualitatively higher level of orderliness (as arranged “in books”) and/or more centralised

¹¹ See, e.g., Robert Melson *Revolution and Genocide On the Origins of the Armenian Genocide and the Holocaust* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press 1996) xxi + 363 pp.

¹² Oswald Spengler *Der Mensch und die Technik Beitrag zu einer Philosophie des Lebens* (München: Beck 1931) v + 88 pp. {*Man and Technics A Contribution to a Philosophy of Law*, transl. Charles Francis Atkinson (New York: Knopf 1932) 104 pp.}

¹³ Cf. Csaba Varga ‘Meeting Points between the Traditions of English–American Common Law and Continental-French Civil Law: Developments and Experience of Postmodernity in Canada’ [2002] in his *Comparative Legal Cultures On Traditions Classified, their Rapprochement & Transfer, and the Anarchy of Hyper-rationalism* (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2012) 253 pp. [*Philosophiae Iuris*] & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15300/15386>>, pp. 105–130 at p. 124.

¹⁴ Cf. Csaba Varga ‘Rule of Law? Mania of Law? On the Boundary between Rationality and Anarchy in America’ [2002] in his *Comparative Legal Cultures*, pp. 165–180, as well as Csaba Varga ‘Law, Ethics, Economy: Independent Paths or Shared Ways?’ [2004] in his *Theory of Law Norm, Logic, System, Doctrine & Technique in Legal Processes, with Appendix on European Law* (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2012) 371 pp. [*Philosophiae Iuris*] & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15400/15409>>, pp. 202–215.

focus (as practiced “in action”), and—either as the main goal or as a side effect—technics enhancing/intensifying the scope and depth of its regulation.

How was the law objectivated and legal knowledge distributed in earlier times?¹⁵ *Codex Hammurapi* once carved; the *Leges Duodecim Tabularum* versed for and memorised by pupils like the child CICERO was expected to do; the *Magna Carta* placarded on church gates once a year; the pre-revolutionary French *cahiers de doléance* as penny literature printed and sold at markets; and all the empirocracy’s laws card-indexed by the once All-Soviet Institute of Legislation,¹⁶ in order to enable the office establishing authoritatively what exactly and with what wording was in force; ending in the Austrian *eGovernment*,¹⁷ which has given a computerised and, thereby, automated answer. What about the future of the laws’ coherence? and of the new instrumentalities making laws and legal changes globally radiated? in a form and with means enabling law to rule society with supreme normative force? while closing any channel through which *mores*, tradition, and common sense could any longer infiltrate it?

It is hard to assess how much the human kind retarded since JEAN-JACQUES ROUSSEAU’s answer to the quest by the Academy of Dijon,¹⁸ but the increasing brutality of warfare and the awakening conscience as the best humanly—humane—reaction have eventually given birth to what is called international humanitarian law. Contrary to the way human conduct is processed in especially criminal law, here it is not facts legally defined that do constitute a case in law, but intent and foresight at the time of tactical planning and commanding execution of military operations—well, these are the new ‘facts’ that are going to be posteriorly reconstrued and assessed, and judged in law.

Or, what role law is dedicated to play at all? As we, in sociology of law in Hungary, back in times of communist dictatorship, already professed, the law’s exclusively effective — optimum — job cannot be more than the reassertion of ongoing social processes by the law’s specific means and authority, that is, a final, symbolic, authoritative stamping. Albeit law is mostly—or too frequently at least—forced into the ugly and impossible role of a *Mädchen für alles*: to act as a demiurge, a substitute to all other means of social reform, taking on what is

¹⁵ Cf. Csaba Varga *Codification as a Socio-historical Phenomenon* (1979/1991) 2nd {reprint} ed. with an Annex & Postscript (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2011) viii + 431 pp. & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14200/14231/>>.

¹⁶ What I visited in Moscow in 1968.

¹⁷ As a break-through by *Digital Austria*, cf. <<http://www.digitales.oesterreich.gv.at/site/6506/default.aspx>> & <<http://www.egov.vic.gov.au/focus-on-countries/europe/countries-europe/austria/trends-and-issues-austria/e-government-austria.html>>, with en European overview in <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/EGovernment_in_Europe#Hungary>.

¹⁸ To the question posed “Has the restoration of the sciences and arts contributed to the purification of morals?” [„Si le rétablissement des sciences et des arts a contribué à épurer les mœurs”], he responded in 1750 that “our souls have become corrupted to the extent that our sciences and our arts have advanced towards perfection.” [„Nos âmes se sont corrompues à mesure que nos sciences et nos arts se sont avancés à la perfection.”] Cf. <https://ebooks.adelaide.edu.au/r/rousseau/jean_jacques/arts/> & <http://classiques.uqac.ca/classiques/Rousseau_jj/discours_sciences_arts/discours_sc_arts.html>.

hardly more than political voluntarism.¹⁹ Albeit making laws—instead of genuine all-social reforms made—is sham action. Otherwise speaking, it is bound to fail while it degrades the law’s prestige, too, at least on the long run.

And in what normative environment and with which expectations is law called to work? For millennia, in integral social organicity, law used to serve cementing community as (a) a frameworking ethos, (b) a prime agent of accumulation of societal experience of transcendence, institutionalised step to step, and (c) the final support of morality, which function became lately assisted also by (d) the lawyers’ professional deontology, classically named as *juristische Weltbild*²⁰. As known, all this has subsequently been denied by the post-1968 Western world, with the very idea of social normativity dissolved under the aegis of libertine individualism and with only law to remain as reduced to the role of a mediator amongst duellers, under conditions of social atomisation with neutral look at law-breakers and law-enforcers alike, just as if all they were nothing else and more than rivalling partners in a sporting event.

3. Changes in Law

It goes without saying that basic changes in how humans are organised into society and in the technology/culture by which their conduct can be and are influenced, may provoke basic changes in law as well.

In the future, possessing already a kind of information technology that enables it to process and taxonomise the whole variety of opinions of millions and to call, directly, masses for public actions, civil society may grow up to the point when, replacing state machinery, it takes power on politically organised society.²¹ For nowadays, by the way, as especially American research in social sciences has shown, random representation of civic opinion is used to prove more prudent, grounded, responsive and responsible as compared to so-called expert opinion, on the one hand. And, though random reaction is characteristically fuzzy or, properly speaking, spread and scattered, in statistical probability their effect is by far foreseeably certain, on the other.

Hardly can anyone foresee now what technics for influencing human behaviour will be operated in future. But perhaps it is enough to recall how much modifications in the implementation of social changes have been assisted by the mass media, new phenomenon of the 20th century, and how extensively the full instrumentality of mass manipulation has been resorted to in both

¹⁹ Cf., e.g., Csaba Varga ‘Macrosociological Theories of Law: A Survey and Appraisal’ [1983/1986] and Csaba Varga ‘The Law and its Limits’ [1985/1992] both in his *Law and Philosophy Selected Papers in Legal Theory* (Budapest: ELTE Project on “Comparative Legal Cultures” 1994) xi + 530 pp. [Philosophiae Iuris] & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15300/15333/#>>, pp. 43–76 respectively 91–96, and, as widely monographed, Kálmán Kulcsár *Modernization and Law* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó 1992) 282 pp.

²⁰ Cf. Friedrich Engels & Karl Krautsky ‘Juristen-Sozialismus’ [1887] in Karl Marx & Friedrich Engels *Werke* 21 (Berlin[-East]: Dietz Verlag 1962), pp. 491–509 & <http://www.mlwerke.de/me/me21/me21_491.htm>.

²¹ E.g. *Global Civil Society Yearbook I*– (London & New York: Oxford University Press 2001–).

dictatorial and democratic regimes of the same century and afterwards. The same holds for social normality as well. For even our present image of personality has already been shocked by such novations like organ transplantation and biotechnics, and the mere technological potential of causing public danger, thanks to means easily available now or in the future, is in itself a challenge to classic freedoms, which are already heavily narrowed, or limited, by antiterrorist measures.²²

Still in its quality of a distinct phenomenon, law, tending also to preserve its own systemicity, develops mostly by changing the volume or extension of its rule-based regulation through narrowing or enlarging (via analogy) the scope it applies to. Any of the components will easily be shaken, as scientific-technical revolution may equally shape organic reproductive processes, disperse information in the electronic space, create virtual realities by projection (I mean here artificial reasons particularly, mastering us already in the field of finances, economic organisation, rule by law, and so on), up to annihilating life on earth—within the limits drawn by the law's general structure and abstract conceptuality.²³

4. Change of Paradigms in the Understanding of Social Order

In the meantime, there has been a change of paradigms in our very understanding of the nature of sociality, of the way action is followed by reaction in the social space of normativity. Until the past mid-century, the physical world outlook once built by NICOLAUS COPERNICUS and ISAAC NEWTON was adapted to social world, too, searching for causes and effects (and isolating them for analytic purposes as much as possible) in the chain of processes. However, the investigation into individual factors (i.e., causes/energies/effects) in those chains of (quasi-)causality was replaced in thermodynamics and sciences on elementary particles about the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, by a vision built on the average of what can be experienced in case of statistic masses and their probabilities. This led to the imagination of half closed, half open systems, exemplified by so-called autopoietic processes, in which the coordinates (or laws) of an ongoing operation are getting defined

²² Cf. the author's memory sitting after the New York World Trade Center collapsed on September 11, 2001, with his friend BJARNE MELKEVIK at the latter's home in Québec, watching US TV channels for news while learning how a terroristic disaster is responded to by those responsible to take a stand on and select priority for prompt necessity over traditionalised routine, involving, if at all, usual limits set by law. Csaba Varga »...*csak múlásunk törvénye*...« Varga Csaba jogfilozófussal beszélget Mezei Károly [»...only our passing away is a law...«: The legal philosopher is interviewed...] (Budapest: Kairosz Kiadó 2012) 142 pp. [Magyarnak lenni CIII] & <<https://www.scribd.com/doc/260367220/csak-mulasunk-torveny-Varga-Csaba-jogfilozofussal-beszelget-Mezei-Karoly>>, pp. 128–129.

²³ Legal machinery permits both discretionary answers and mutually contradictory conclusions to be drawn from the same wording, once there is support by sufficiently motivated legal reasoning, digging deep enough in what is meant by law; cf. Csaba Varga 'Judicial Black-box and the Rule of Law in the Context of European Unification and Globalisation' [2008] in his *Theory of Law*, pp. 225–242.

through (while and for) the operational process itself, that is, individually for each case. Accordingly, the idea of »order out of chaos«, unthinkable beforehand for both scientific and theological reasons, became the explanation for micro-physics and—gradually—for anthropology, sociology, and the legal field as well.²⁴ Moreover, treating law as just one of the considerations rather than the sole *definitivum*,²⁵ it became identified as the operational principle making the European Union work as well: the union and the national states, i.e., union laws and domestic laws challenging / responding to one another, and creating eventually thereby, from apparent diversity (close to sheer anarchy for micro-analysis), an unprecedentedly high level of law and order (at macro-level).²⁶

Accordingly, oriented toward individual actors/acts and their inherent teleology, classical legal positivism is to respond to classical physical world outlook, while the »order out of chaos« vision—with a concept of order extended from micro-physics to the universe of the humans' world — corresponds to the stand taken by contemporary anthropology, sociology, and legal scholarship. In neo-KANTianism, methodological purity was a *sine qua non*. Now, in the legal regime of the European Union, member-states continue following the old paradigm whilst their interaction both amongst them and with the European Union law proper, exhibits the new paradigm's features.²⁷

It might be seen as symptomatic that in the twentieth year of the *Internationales Rechtsinformatisches Symposia* at Salzburg, there is a standing section devoted to *Science Fiction & Utopia*.²⁸ For since the time of ALDOUS HUXLEY's *Brave New World* (1931), the world may have changed, but the past's vision of ARTHUR KOESTLER's *Darkness at Noon* (1940) so much as the totalitarian technicality forevisioned by GEORGE ORWELL's *Animal Farm* (1945)²⁹ have proved to be underestimated, compared with the hidden moves of historical reality.

Law tends to be conservative but, as known, within its own system of justification, optional technics with contradictory outcomes tolerate, permit, and sometimes expressly call for complete turns, with genuine volte-face, in judicial

²⁴ Cf. Varga *The Paradigms of Legal Thinking*.

²⁵ According to Gunther Teubner 'Legal Irritants: Good Faith in British Law or How Unifying Law Ends up in New Divergences' *The Modern Law Review* 61 (1998) 1, pp. 11–32 and especially p. 12, any imposed texture in law is going to become a factor of trouble so long as finally it is either rejected or made to function properly. See also Csaba Varga 'Transfers of Law: A Conceptual Analysis' [2003] in his *Comparative Legal Cultures*, pp. 181–208.

²⁶ Csaba Varga 'Legal Theorising: An Unrecognised Need for Practicing the European Law' [2009] in his *Theory of Law*, pp. 307–354.

²⁷ Or, a normative piece of information is issued by a union agency and, then, reacted to by some domestic agency, which then gets reacted/disputed/retorted to by any union or state level agency calling on domestic/union reconsideration, which latter will be responded to by a second union agency piece of information—which looks like a game itself, played/playable to infinity.

²⁸ Cf. <<http://www.univie.ac.at/RI/IRIS2013/>>.

²⁹ Cf. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brave_New_World>, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Darkness_at_Noon> & <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Animal_Farm>.

interpretation and construction. In accordance with it, possible renewals of law will mostly be the result of what we do perceive of as prerequisites of social/societal existence. This is to say that our present-day preference to preserving free choice if stately and individual entities will necessarily be counter-balanced (if not overruled) by the priority of what the security of bare community existence demands under new conditions. Perhaps the centuries old fight for liberty in modern times will be remembered with resignation and nostalgia, a failed Golden Age Two, too.

In contemporary public speech, buzzwords like ‘natural law’, ‘constitutionality’, ‘human rights’, and ‘the Rule of Law’, are highly popularised and defended as highest-valued goals themselves, although none of them can be an exception to the main—ontological—rule. For they stand for nothing but instrumental values within the realm of law. Consequently, their genuine value is a function of what fundamental values they mediate. Or, in the subsequent era of scientific-technological revolution, they may also be exposed to transformation hitherto unimagined/unimaginable.³⁰

Summing up, even some decades ago visions of future could be outlined through present tendencies extrapolated, for the former could only be as experienced by the accumulation of the latter’s various and varying shifts of emphasis. As to the present—the fact notwithstanding that the 20th century interwar period was already imprinted with the widespread feeling of *Weltkrise*³¹—, not event directions can be taken as granted.³² The future will emerge from actions still to be carried out. In conclusion, a long series of alternatives is the only help to preview anything from the future.

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³⁰ Csaba Varga ‘Buts et moyens en droit’ in *Giovanni Paolo II Le vie della giustizia: Itinerari per il terzo millennio* (Omaggio dei giuristi a Sua Santità nel XXV anno di pontificato) a cura di Aldo Loiodice & Massimo Vari (Roma: Bardi Editore & Libreria Editrice Vaticana 2003), pp. 71–75, with full text in his *Theory of Law*, pp. 189–201.

³¹ As to best Hungarian approach with international bibliography, cf. Béla Hamvas *A világválság* [World crisis] (Budapest: Budapest Székesfőváros Házinyomdája 1938) 69 pp. [= *A Fővárosi Könyvtár évkönyve VII* (1937), pp. 39–105]. The very crisis of “human existence” itself is treated by sociologist Elemér Hankiss ‘Európa, két világ közt’ [Europe between two worlds] *Magyar Tudomány* CLXXIV (2013) 11, pp. 1386–1395 & <<http://www.matud.iif.hu/2013/11/15.htm>>.

³² Noticed by the Hungarian Prime Minister VIKTOR ORBÁN who raised the issue in private discussion with the author while closed meeting at Saloon Hermina on November 30, 2012.